

ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons, Goods, and Establishment and Implications on Regional Insecurity: Nigeria Perspective

Chijiohe Basil Onuoha¹, Reuben Clifford Wilson^{2*}

¹ Department of Public Administration, University of Uyo, Uyo Akwa Ibom State.

^{2*} Department of Political Science, University of Uyo, Uyo Akwa Ibom State.

***Correspondence:** Reuben Clifford Wilson

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ABSTRACT: The ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons, Goods, and the Right of Establishment, adopted in 1979, was designed to foster regional integration by allowing the unrestricted movement of people, goods, and services across West African member states. While Nigeria benefited from increased trade, investment, and cultural exchange, the implementation of the protocol also brought about significant security and economic challenges. This study assessed the security threats associated with the ECOWAS Protocol, with a particular focus on Nigeria's North-East region. A historical-descriptive approach was used for the study, which relied on both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were gathered through ten key informant interviews involving government officials, security experts, and policy practitioners to gain firsthand insights into the operational realities of the ECOWAS Protocol. These interviews provided qualitative evidence regarding the security and economic impacts of regional mobility. Secondary data were obtained from official reports, peer-reviewed academic journals, ECOWAS documents, and international policy briefs, which provided crucial information on crime patterns, enforcement gaps, and

trade irregularities. The findings revealed that the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons inadvertently facilitated human trafficking in Nigeria. Traffickers exploited weak border controls, informal crossing points, and fraudulent ECOWAS documents to move victims, particularly women and minors, through border towns such as Seme, Jibia, and Illela. Similarly, the Protocol on Free Movement of Goods facilitated the smuggling of small arms and light weapons (SALWs), often hidden within legal cargo and transported through unregulated routes, fueling violence in states like Borno, Zamfara, and Katsina. Additionally, the Right of Establishment provision was misused by smugglers who set up front companies to divert subsidized petroleum products across borders. The study recommended the implementation of a regional biometric identity verification system and the establishment of a robust intelligence-sharing framework among ECOWAS security agencies to improve border security and regional cooperation.

Keywords: *ECOWAS, Free Movement Protocol, Human Trafficking, Small Arms, Smuggling, Petroleum Diversion, Border Security, Regional Cooperation.*

Introduction

The contemporary global system is increasingly marked by interdependence and complexity, making it challenging for individual nation-states to function in isolation. This growing interconnectedness has led many regions, including West Africa, to pursue regional integration as a strategy to foster economic development, political cooperation, and collective security. In 1975, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) was established through the Treaty of Lagos, with the primary goal of promoting economic integration and self-reliance among its member states (Ezenwe, 1983). Over time, ECOWAS expanded its mandate to include socio-economic cooperation, political stability, and peacebuilding across the region (Adebayo, 2014).

A major milestone in ECOWAS's integration efforts came in 1979 with the adoption of the Protocol on Free Movement of Persons, Residence, and Establishment (Protocol A/P.1/5/1979). This protocol was designed to facilitate the movement of citizens within the ECOWAS region, allowing them to enter, reside, and establish

economic activities freely in member states without visas or permits. The aim was to promote intra-regional trade, labor mobility, investment, and a shared sense of West African identity, under the belief that these factors would stimulate regional growth and development (Adepoju, 2002; Kouyaté, 2013; Olayiwola & Okodua, 2020). However, the open-border policy has introduced significant security challenges, which have increasingly undermined the intended benefits of the protocol. While the free movement of people was meant to foster economic integration, it has also facilitated the proliferation of transnational crimes, including terrorism, human trafficking, smuggling, and arms proliferation (Onuoha, 2013). A key example of this is the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria's North-East, which has been exacerbated by the ease with which militants can cross borders from neighboring ECOWAS states such as Niger, Chad, and Cameroon, complicating Nigeria's counterterrorism efforts (Adebayo, 2014).

The free movement policy has also been exploited by human trafficking networks, facilitating the illegal transport of individuals especially women and children—across West African borders. Nigeria, serving as both a source and destination country for trafficking, has seen victims routed through neighboring states like Niger, Mali, and Burkina Faso en route to Europe (UNODC, 2018). Furthermore, the smuggling of goods, particularly petroleum products, has escalated due to lax border controls. As Africa's largest oil producer, Nigeria has suffered significant economic losses from the illicit transportation of subsidized fuel to neighboring countries with higher market prices. This smuggling depletes national resources and fuels criminal networks (Federal Republic of Nigeria v. Tunde Owolabi, 2015).

Compounding these issues is the proliferation of small arms and light weapons across Nigeria's porous borders. The availability of such weapons has intensified violent conflicts, particularly in the northern regions of Nigeria, involving herders, farmers, armed militias, and insurgents. This proliferation has exacerbated national security concerns, with violent crimes such as kidnapping, cattle rustling, and armed robbery becoming more prevalent in Nigeria's North-East, North-West, and North-Central regions.

In recognition of these threats, ECOWAS has introduced several measures to mitigate the negative impacts of the free movement protocol. These measures include the establishment of the ECOWAS Conflict Prevention Framework (ECPF), the creation of national focal points on small arms, and enhanced cooperation between customs and immigration agencies. Additionally, the 1999 Mechanism for Conflict Prevention, Management, Resolution, Peacekeeping, and Security was introduced to coordinate regional responses to security challenges (ECOWAS Commission, 2006). Despite these efforts, transnational crimes continue to thrive, and Nigeria's security situation remains precarious. The security challenges facing Nigeria and the broader West African sub-region go beyond traditional military threats to include illicit activities such as arms proliferation, human trafficking, and smuggling. These issues have had profound implications for national and regional stability. According to recent data, Nigeria has over 1 million small arms in circulation, contributing to widespread violence and instability (The Punch, 2023). The smuggling of goods, particularly petroleum products, has cost Nigeria billions in lost revenue, undermining the country's economic stability (World Bank, 2016). The trafficking of people has also escalated, with 2,880 victims registered in 2022, a dramatic increase from the 700 victims in 2017.

In response, Nigeria has invested in border surveillance technologies, including biometric registration and electronic monitoring systems, to improve border control and reduce illicit activities. Additionally, Nigeria has strengthened regional cooperation, notably through the Nigeria-Cameroon Joint Task Force, to address cross-border security issues. Legal reforms have also been enacted, such as the Nigerian Trafficking in Persons Enforcement and Administration Act (2003), and the National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) has been established to combat trafficking (Ibrahim, 2020). Despite these efforts, the security threats persist. The role of regional conventions, especially ECOWAS's free movement protocol, in exacerbating these security challenges has not been adequately explored. This study seeks to investigate the implications of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons, Goods, and Establishment on regional security, particularly in Nigeria.

Specific Objectives:

- i. To examine how E COWAS protocol on free movement of persons account for human trafficking in Nigeria
- ii. To assess the level to which ECOWAS protocol on free movement of goods enhance illicit arm use in Nigeria
- iii. To investigate how ECOWAS protocol on Establishment Sustain Petroleum and other Product Smuggling in Nigeria.

Research Design

To achieved the above listed objectives, the researchers adopted historical descriptive research design. This entailed the utilization of qualitative research approach. Qualitative research approach is a combination of research principles using unstructured forms of data collections, verbal descriptions and explanations rather than quantitative measurement and statistical analysis. Data for this study were collected from both primary and secondary sources. Data were gathered from official reports, academic journals, and other relevant publications. Reports from government agencies, security organizations, and ECOWAS offered authoritative information on policy implementation and enforcement. Peer-reviewed academic journals provided research and analyses on the economic and security dimensions of the protocol. Additionally, policy briefs, research papers, and data from international organizations were analyzed to assess trends in crime rates, border security incidents, and economic indicators.

In view of the nature of this study, the study employed content and textual analysis. In doing this, the study sieved and analyzed the volume of data found in audio taping, official documents, field note taking, news papers, books and journal used in this study. Textual analysis is a research techniques used to make replicable and valid interferences by interpreting and coding text material. By systematically evaluating texts (e.g transcribed audio taping communication and documents). Content and textual analysis allows researcher to rivet in the underlying ideological presupposition of text. It reaches beyond luculent contents to understand the

prevailing ideologies of particular historical and cultural moment that make a specific coverage possible

Review of Conceptual and Operational Framework

a. Concept of ECOWAS Protocol on free movement of person, goods and establishment

The ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons, Goods, and Establishment, established in 1979, serves as a critical framework for fostering economic integration among West African states. This protocol is designed to facilitate seamless cross-border movement, allowing individuals, goods, and businesses to operate across member states with minimal restrictions. By removing barriers to trade and mobility, the protocol aims to create a unified regional market, which is expected to enhance economic cooperation and growth within West Africa (ECOWAS, 1979).

From an economic perspective, the ECOWAS Protocol is a strategic initiative aimed at promoting regional economic development by eliminating tariffs and trade barriers that impede the free exchange of goods and services (Adepoju, 2002). This policy is intended to stimulate intra-regional commerce, attract investment, and increase economic activity across the member states. The protocol also grants citizens of member countries the right to travel, reside, and work freely within the region, thereby facilitating labor mobility and integrating the regional workforce (Boas, 2018). This unrestricted movement is expected to foster economic dynamism and cultural exchange among the diverse populations of West Africa.

Legally, the protocol provides a standardized framework that governs the free movement of persons and goods, setting out the rights and obligations of member states to ensure uniform implementation (ECOWAS, 1979). It establishes a legal basis for economic cooperation and integration, ensuring that member states adhere to common policies and regulations. This legal framework is crucial for maintaining consistency and coherence in regional economic practices.

However, the protocol's implementation also presents significant security challenges. The ease of cross-border movement has been exploited by criminal networks and

militant groups, such as Boko Haram, who use the open borders to conduct illegal activities, including arms trafficking, smuggling, and terrorism (Onuoha, 2013). These security risks undermine the stability and safety of the region, revealing a critical tension between the goals of economic integration and the need for effective security measures. The proliferation of small arms and the rise in transnational crime are direct consequences of the protocol's open borders policy, posing substantial threats to regional stability (Aning and Eizenga, 2019).

The ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons, Goods, and Establishment represents a significant effort to integrate West African economies by promoting the free flow of people, goods, and services. While it aims to boost regional economic growth and cooperation, it also introduces security challenges that must be addressed to ensure that the benefits of economic integration do not come at the expense of regional stability and safety (UNCTAD, 2019). The protocol's dual impact on economic development and security highlights the need for a balanced approach that integrates economic policies with robust security measures to safeguard the region's overall well-being.

b. Concept of Regional Insecurity

Before defining what regional insecurity entails, it is pertinent to define what constitutes insecurity. Insecurity, a multifaceted concept, can be examined through various perspectives, including political, sociological, economic, security studies, and psychological lenses. From a political science standpoint, insecurity is the exposure to threats resulting from ineffective governance and political instability. This condition is often marked by violence and the state's failure to maintain order and protect its citizens (Ogunleye, 2018). Sociologically, insecurity refers to the vulnerability experienced by individuals or communities due to social, economic, or environmental factors, which undermine their safety and well-being (Akintoye, 2020). Economically, insecurity is characterized by instability and uncertainty in economic life, influenced by unemployment, poverty, and inadequate access to resources, which can exacerbate social unrest and broader instability (Ibrahim & Alabi, 2019). In the context of security studies, insecurity encompasses threats to safety and welfare, including conflicts, terrorism, and organized crime, reflecting the

inadequacies of security systems in addressing these challenges (Adeniran, 2021). Psychologically, insecurity describes the emotional state of feeling threatened or unsafe, leading to anxiety and stress due to perceived or actual dangers in the environment (Ogunyemi, 2022). Each perspective highlights different aspects of insecurity, from structural and economic issues to emotional and security system failures, with local authors providing insights into the unique experiences and challenges faced within specific contexts.

Regional insecurity on the other hands refers to a state of heightened risk and instability within a region, characterized by persistent threats and challenges that compromise the safety and order of member states (UNDP, 2021). It encompasses conditions where internal and external factors contribute to a breakdown in regional stability, often leading to conflicts, violence, and political turmoil (Fawcett, 2005). Regional insecurity arises from various sources, including armed conflicts, terrorism, and organized crime, which disrupt the security and cohesion of the region (Møller, 2018).

The presence of persistent threats such as insurgencies, ethnic conflicts, and cross-border crime exacerbates regional insecurity, making it difficult for states to effectively manage and mitigate these challenges (Hancock, 2017). For example, the activities of Boko Haram and other insurgent groups have significantly contributed to regional insecurity in West Africa by causing widespread violence and instability (Adebajo, 2019). Similarly, the proliferation of small arms and organized crime undermines efforts to maintain security and stability, creating an environment of persistent insecurity (UNODC, 2020).

Regional insecurity is further compounded by factors such as political instability, corruption, and economic difficulties, which undermine the effectiveness of security measures and contribute to ongoing unrest (Olayiwola&Okodua, 2020). The inability of regional states to effectively address and manage these threats often results in a cycle of violence and instability that challenges the effectiveness of security frameworks and cooperative efforts (Boas, 2018). For instance, political conflicts and electoral violence in Nigeria have exacerbated regional insecurity by creating conditions of instability and unrest (Harris, 2020).The impact of regional insecurity

is widespread, affecting not only the immediate safety of member states but also hindering economic development and social progress within the region (Söderbaum, 2007). The disruption of regional peace and stability caused by ongoing conflicts, crime, and other forms of violence undermines cooperative security efforts and contributes to a state of persistent insecurity (Guzzini, 2000).

Review of Empirical Literature

The ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons, Goods, and Establishment has been widely examined in relation to its impact on regional security in Nigeria. For example, Aminu (2019) conducted a study titled "Permeable Borders and Insecurity: The ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement and Trans-Border Banditry on the Nigeria-Niger Republic Frontier." The study emphasizes that the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), established in 1975 as a sub-regional organization, was primarily aimed at promoting economic cooperation among member states. To achieve this goal, the ECOWAS protocol on freedom of movement and the right of residency for citizens of member states was adopted in 1979. This protocol aimed to create a borderless sub-region through a single market, shared currency, and a free tariff zone. Despite its continued implementation over the past four decades, the protocol has been challenged by numerous trans-border security issues affecting the sub-region. This study specifically investigates the connection between the protocol and trans-border banditry along the Nigeria-Niger Republic frontier. Utilizing economic integration theory, the research gathered quantitative data through questionnaires distributed to 400 respondents from the study area. Data analysis was conducted using cross-tabulation, simple percentages, and Chi-Square techniques. The study found that the ongoing implementation of the protocol has significantly contributed to the porosity of the Nigeria-Niger Republic border, facilitating undocumented migration and making the border a conduit for arms trafficking and banditry. While acknowledging the positive impacts of ECOWAS on member states, the study recommends that Nigeria should remain a member of ECOWAS but consider opting out of the protocol to better control trans-border banditry along the Nigeria-Niger frontier.

Supporting this finding, Ajibola and Ayomola (2022) conducted an "Assessment of the Consequences of ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement on Nigeria's National Security." The study highlighted that movement within the ECOWAS sub-region has been both voluntary and forced, particularly since the end of the Cold War when national security policies became a priority. The security landscape in Nigeria has been compromised by incidents of banditry, kidnapping, militancy, terrorism, farmer-herder conflicts, and ethno-religious tensions, which have adversely affected both economic and security policies. These security challenges are prevalent not only in Nigeria but also in neighboring countries like Benin, Niger, Chad, and Cameroon. The study employed a quantitative approach, surveying 319 respondents from the Nigerian Immigration Service and Nigerian Customs Service. Two key findings emerged: first, the ECOWAS protocol has had a significantly negative impact on the safety of people and property in Nigeria, and second, it has adversely affected national security to a considerable extent. The study recommended that the government should enhance border security and ensure the full implementation of the ECOWAS protocol on free movement among member states.

Andrew (2019) explored the broader regional security framework in his study "Africa's Regional Approach to Conflict Prevention, Security Management: ECOWAS Vision 2020 – Peace, Human Rights, and Security." This research reviews ECOWAS's role in promoting peace, human rights, and security in West Africa through its Vision 2020 initiative. ECOWAS aims to create a peaceful and conducive environment for cooperation and regional integration, which is viewed as a critical tool for accelerating economic development in West Africa. The Vision 2020 plan, adopted in June 2007, focuses on facilitating free movement, enhancing access to education and health, promoting economic activities, and improving living standards. This paper examines ECOWAS's efforts to achieve peace, human rights, and stability within this framework, identifying areas needing review to enhance the effectiveness of peace and security initiatives.

Iringe (2021) provides further insights into regional security dynamics in his study, "ECOWAS and the Control of Arms Trafficking: Implications for Regional Security." The research asserts that the proliferation of illicit arms in West Africa, often utilized

by both state and non-state actors, poses a severe threat surpassing even the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of socio-economic impact. This study examines the ECOWAS Convention and its role in controlling illicit arms in the region, grounded in Adam Smith's rational choice theory. Employing a descriptive methodology and relying on secondary data from library research, articles, textbooks, and internet publications, the study reveals that over 100 million illicit arms circulate in West Africa, exacerbating armed conflicts despite ECOWAS's efforts to curb arms trafficking. The research concludes that the ECOWAS Convention's objectives to regulate illicit arms remain unmet due to weak national controls and a lack of international cooperation. The paper calls for a new approach with clearer objectives among ECOWAS member states to combat the illicit arms trade and prevent their transfer to criminals, terrorists, and combatants.

In another significant study, Adebayo (2021) analyzed the effects of the ECOWAS protocol on Nigeria's internal security, revealing through qualitative analysis that the protocol has strained the country's security infrastructure, contributing to a rise in illicit activities such as smuggling and illegal immigration. The study recommended a review of the protocol to incorporate more stringent security measures and improve inter-agency collaboration to mitigate these risks. Olaniyi (2021) also evaluated the impact of the protocol on insecurity in Nigeria, particularly in border areas. The study, which used statistical analysis and thematic analysis of data collected from border community residents, found a direct correlation between the implementation of the protocol and increased insecurity, underscoring the need for enhanced regional security cooperation and border community policing.

Further research by Musa (2020) examined the link between transnational crime and regional integration under the ECOWAS Protocol. Through document analysis and expert interviews, Musa's study found that the protocol has facilitated transnational crime, including drug trafficking and arms smuggling, posing a significant threat to regional security. He recommended developing a regional crime prevention strategy and improving intelligence sharing among member states to address these challenges. Similarly, Ojo (2019) investigated the challenges and prospects of border security under the ECOWAS protocol. The research, which involved field observations and

interviews with border security personnel, concluded that the protocol has complicated border security operations in Nigeria, leading to increased smuggling and illegal immigration. The study suggested the implementation of comprehensive border management systems and greater cross-border cooperation as solutions.

Adedokun (2022) focused on ECOWAS's role in addressing transnational security threats under the Free Movement Protocol. By interviewing ECOWAS officials and analyzing regional security reports, the study found that while ECOWAS has made efforts to address security threats, significant challenges remain in fully implementing these measures across member states. The study recommended strengthening ECOWAS's capacity to enforce security protocols and improving compliance among member states. Lastly, Nwankwo (2021) analyzed the impact of the ECOWAS Free Movement Protocol on human security in Nigeria, particularly in border regions. His mixed-methods study, combining surveys and in-depth interviews with affected communities, found that while the protocol has facilitated regional integration, it has also led to human security challenges, especially in terms of health and safety. The study concluded that regional integration efforts must consider the broader implications for human security and recommended policies that address the social and economic impacts of the protocol on local communities, alongside enhanced public health measures in border regions.

These studies collectively underscore the complex interplay between regional integration and security within the framework of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons, Goods, and Establishment. They highlight the need for a balanced approach that promotes economic cooperation while addressing the significant security risks associated with the protocol. The recommendations across these studies point towards the necessity of strengthened border management, enhanced regional cooperation, and comprehensive strategies to mitigate the security challenges posed by the free movement provisions in the protocol.

ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons and Human Trafficking in Nigeria: An Assessment.

The **ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons, Residence, and Establishment**, signed in 1979, was designed to promote **regional integration**,

economic cooperation, and **people-to-people interaction** across West Africa. By granting citizens of member states the right to enter, reside, and establish economic activities in other ECOWAS countries for up to 90 days without a visa, the protocol aimed to ease mobility and stimulate trade and employment across borders (ECOWAS, 2019). While these objectives have contributed to regional unity and intra-African trade, the **liberal provisions** of the protocol have also **unintentionally facilitated human trafficking**, particularly in **Nigeria**, which occupies a central geographical and political position in the ECOWAS sub-region.

By the early **2000s**, Nigeria began emerging as a **key node in regional and global human trafficking networks**. The **United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC)** has consistently classified Nigeria as a **source, transit, and destination country** for trafficking victims, with significant flows of women and children trafficked for **forced labor, sexual exploitation, and domestic servitude** (UNODC, 2020). As traffickers took advantage of **relaxed residency requirements and poor border control**, cities such as **Lagos, Benin City, and Kano** evolved into **hotspots and transit points** for victims moving from countries like **Ghana, Burkina Faso, and Togo** into and through Nigeria (Ogunleye and Ojo, 2022).

By **2019**, the **International Organization for Migration (IOM)** revealed that over **60% of irregular migrants** intercepted in West Africa had crossed **at least two ECOWAS borders** using **unofficial transport channels**, often without being subjected to formal checks. The use of **informal motor parks, unapproved bush paths, and manipulated ECOWAS identity documents** became common strategies adopted by trafficking networks (IOM, 2019). The **Seme Border in Lagos** and **Jibia in Katsina State** were identified as particularly vulnerable to exploitation due to **minimal scrutiny and limited surveillance infrastructure** (Eze and Onyekwere, 2023). Between **2015 and 2022**, the **National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP)** documented thousands of cases involving ECOWAS nationals. Victims from **Niger, Benin, and Togo** were trafficked into Nigeria for **domestic servitude**, while Nigerian nationals especially from **Edo, Delta, and Kano States** were trafficked out to **Libya, Italy, and Spain** under false promises of employment or education (NAPTIP, 2022). These victims, often women

and minors, ended up in **brothels, forced labor camps**, or under conditions of **modern-day slavery**.

In 2021, the **U.S. Trafficking in Persons (TIP) Report** placed **Nigeria on the Tier 2 Watchlist**, citing the country's **inadequate efforts to combat trafficking** despite the scale of the problem. This designation had diplomatic and financial implications, **limiting Nigeria's access to certain categories of international aid** and cooperation (Okonkwo, 2022). Beyond the human rights violations, the **economic impact of trafficking is profound**. Trafficking depletes Nigeria's **human capital**, particularly through the exploitation of young and able-bodied women and children who would otherwise contribute to the **productive economy**. The **loss of labor productivity**, coupled with the rise in associated crimes such as drug use, prostitution, and fraudulent enterprises, undermines both **economic growth** and **social cohesion** (Osei and Boateng, 2022). Additionally, the proliferation of **drug routes and local methamphetamine labs**, closely linked to the same informal trafficking networks, has fueled a **public health crisis**. The **National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA)** has reported a sharp increase in **drug abuse** and seizures across Lagos, Kano, and Port Harcourt, intensifying Nigeria's youth crime problem and further deterring foreign investment (Adeoye, 2022).

One of the structural weaknesses enabling this trafficking pattern is the **absence of an integrated biometric identity system** within ECOWAS, coupled with **poor coordination among immigration, customs, and law enforcement agencies**. The **lack of real-time regional databases** makes it difficult to monitor and verify the identities of people moving between member states. This gap is frequently exploited by **trafficking syndicates**, many of which operate with transnational connections and political protection in some cases (Akinyemi and Afolabi, 2020). In response to these challenges, **ECOWAS launched a Plan of Action against Trafficking in Persons (2008–2011)**, with extended frameworks introduced in later years. These initiatives emphasized **cross-border cooperation, capacity building, and harmonization of anti-trafficking laws**. However, implementation has remained weak, especially in **border communities** where **state presence is minimal** and **governance is fragmented** (UNODC, 2021).

Collaborating with the earlier positions, insights from key informant interview conducted with security operatives in North-East Nigeria on 21st April 2024 revealed deeper concerns about the systemic vulnerabilities exploited by human trafficking syndicates under the ECOWAS Free Movement framework. Thus:

“Security operatives reiterated that Nigeria’s extensive and poorly monitored borders with Benin, Niger, and Cameroon have created unchecked corridors for human trafficking. According to an immigration officer from Yobe State, many traffickers avoid formal checkpoints entirely, using bush paths, dry riverbeds, and informal transport routes, especially in Borno, Adamawa, and Taraba States. The officer emphasized: Our biggest challenge is not just at the official borders; it’s the hundreds of unofficial routes that are impossible to fully secure with current manpower and logistics.”

Another major concern raised by respondent was the acute shortage of personnel’s manning the borders. According to him, the acute shortage of logistics and personnel at key border points, highlighting that many posts operate with minimal staff and lack basic operational tools such as patrol vehicles, communication devices, and night surveillance equipment. This inadequacy, he explained, makes it extremely difficult to monitor cross-border activities, especially during nighttime when traffickers often exploit the cover of darkness. The officer further noted that the limited number of officers on duty creates fatigue and reduces vigilance, allowing traffickers to bribe their way through checkpoints with ease, thereby undermining national security efforts.

The security officials also pointed out the absence of biometric identity verification and a unified ECOWAS-wide traveler database as major facilitators of cross-border trafficking. An operative from NAPTIP based in Maiduguri explained that traffickers frequently manipulate ECOWAS identification cards or travel with forged documents, which cannot be authenticated at remote border outposts due to a lack of real-time data systems. “We’ve intercepted several traffickers with fake ECOWAS IDs or documents bearing aliases. Without biometric verification, it’s difficult to

determine their true identity or previous offences in other ECOWAS countries,” the officer noted. This technological gap enables repeat offenders to traffic individuals across borders with impunity, often recycling routes and shifting operations between ECOWAS countries depending on enforcement intensity.

Furthermore, the operatives confirmed that victims are lured under false pretenses of job offers, scholarships, or marriage opportunities. According to a senior immigration officer from Adamawa: “Victims, especially girls aged 13–18, are recruited in rural villages with promises of working in hair salons, schools, or households in Ghana, Senegal, or Italy. Once across the border, they are handed over to syndicates who force them into prostitution or unpaid domestic work.” Trafficking flows are bidirectional. The operatives cited examples where Nigeriens and Togolese women were intercepted in transit to Lagos and Kano, and where Nigerian girls were being moved through the Chad-Cameroon corridor en route to North Africa and Europe. Several officials mentioned Edo, Delta, Kano, and Borno States as prominent source states, while Lagos, Sokoto, Katsina, and Benin City were identified as major transit and destination hubs within Nigeria.

In another development, the respondent revealed that inter-agency rivalry and weak coordination between national and ECOWAS-level security bodies hinder effective responses. A Civil Defence officer from Bauchi explained: “We often work in silos. NAPTIP might be tracking a case, but without coordination with the Immigration Service or Customs, the traffickers pass unnoticed. We need a single database, joint task forces, and continuous inter-agency briefings.” Moreover, security agencies lack access to ECOWAS-wide arrest warrants or alert systems, meaning that traffickers wanted in one country can seek refuge in another with little fear of extradition or arrest.

The role of Corruption and Political Protection was no left out, a candid contribution from a senior Customs official pointed to corruption among border officials as a major enabler. According to the officer:

There are known traffickers who regularly cross the borders because they pay their way through. Without robust oversight

and disciplinary mechanisms, even the best policy cannot work.” The operatives stressed that some trafficking rings enjoy political protection, especially in remote areas where state presence is weak or local elites have vested interests in cross-border businesses.

The following data from the table shows the numbers of recurs victims of human trafficking in the region from 2017-2023

Table 4.1: Data Analysis of Rescued Victims for human Trafficking in Nigeria: 2017 – 2023

Reported Cases	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
External trafficking for sexual exploitation	113	112	62	152	226	186	139
Internal trafficking for sexual exploitation	48	58	89	80	55	58	39
External trafficking for labour exploitation	NA*	69	26	21	39	25	1
Internal trafficking for labour exploitation	273	197	169	302	53	96	65
Nigerians deported as illegal migrants	8	73	9	44	14	21	21
Child labour	207	89	63	100	205	212	169
Child abuse	166	110	88	64	60	37	55
Child abduction from guardianship	2	4	1	5	4	8	35
Forced marriage	2	4	2	1	0	3	2
Rape/sexual abuse	5	10	36	34	16	4	7
Others	357	231	470	173	77	314	500
Total	1181	957	1015	976	749	964	1030

Source: NAPTIP Human Trafficking Reports, 2017-2023

ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Illicit Arm Use in Nigeria: the Nexus

The **ECOWAS Protocol on the Free Movement of Persons, Residence, and Establishment**, adopted in 1979, was a landmark policy aimed at fostering regional integration, economic cooperation, and socio-political collaboration across West Africa. Paired with the **ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme (ETLS)**, the protocol sought to eliminate barriers to intra-regional mobility and trade. While these frameworks have facilitated economic growth and cross-border commerce, their liberal provisions have inadvertently opened up security gaps, particularly in Nigeria.

One of the earliest and most persistent security challenges has been **unregulated migration**. Nigeria's vast and poorly monitored borders 1,608 km with Niger, 1,690 km with Cameroon, 773 km with Benin, and 85 km with Chad serve as conduits for unauthorized entries (Olawale, 2021). The **Nigerian Immigration Service (NIS)** has reported frequent incursions through illegal routes, often by individuals without valid identification documents (Ogunleye & Ojo, 2022). The **absence of a harmonized biometric database across ECOWAS** states further weakens the capacity of border authorities to differentiate between legitimate travelers and criminal infiltrators (Adebayo, 2021). These border vulnerabilities have been exploited by **violent extremist groups**, especially Boko Haram and the Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP). These groups have used **unsecured entry points** along Nigeria's northeastern borders with Niger and Chad to launch cross-border attacks. Intelligence sources confirm that insurgents routinely escape military offensives by retreating into neighboring countries, regrouping, and re-entering Nigeria through **unguarded bush paths** (Ajayi, 2022; Ibrahim & Yusuf, 2020).

Compounding this threat is the **proliferation of small arms and light weapons (SALWs)**. Criminal syndicates smuggle weapons from **conflict-ridden countries like Libya, Mali, and Niger** into northern Nigeria, particularly through porous border regions (Ogunleye & Ojo, 2022). These arms fuel insurgency in the Northeast, banditry in the Northwest, and herder-farmer conflicts in the Middle Belt. According to the **UNODC (2019)**, West Africa harbors over 350 million illicit firearms, with Nigeria accounting for nearly 70% of this cache. These weapons often

arrive hidden in shipments of second-hand goods or are smuggled alongside legitimate cargo under lax inspection protocols.

Armed banditry has escalated in states such as Zamfara, Katsina, Sokoto, and Niger, often perpetrated by ex-combatants from previous civil wars in Liberia, Sierra Leone, Chad, and Mali (Vines, 2004; Ezeanyika & Ubah, 2012). These groups carry out kidnappings, cattle rustling, and armed robberies with increasing coordination and brutality. Reports indicate that Nigerian Customs occasionally intercept arms shipments at seaports like Apapa and Tin Can Island, but many more evade detection due to **corruption and inadequate surveillance systems**. The protocol has also enabled the **unregulated movement of nomadic pastoralists**, particularly Fulani herders from Niger, Mali, and Chad. These migrations into Nigeria's Middle Belt have led to **herder-farmer conflicts**, especially in Benue, Plateau, and Taraba States (Ajayi, 2022). The resulting disputes over grazing land and water resources have triggered violence, leading to massive displacement and ethnic tensions (Ibrahim & Yusuf, 2020). Armed herders, emboldened by access to smuggled weapons, have intensified these clashes. In urban areas such as Lagos, Benin City, and Port Harcourt, the **proliferation of arms** has contributed to rising cult-related violence, organized crime, and criminal gang activity. The **illicit arms trade**, valued globally at over \$3.5 billion in 2014 (UNODC, 2016), continues to supply a wide range of non-state actors operating within and across Nigerian borders.

Another major security issue is **drug trafficking**. Nigeria has emerged as a key transit hub for narcotics from Latin America especially cocaine from Brazil and Colombia—moving through West Africa into Europe (Alemika, 2013). ECOWAS free movement clauses are routinely exploited by traffickers to move drugs via Guinea-Bissau, Ghana, and Benin through Nigeria's Southwest corridor, including states like Ogun and Oyo (Ibrahim & Yusuf, 2020). The **NDLEA** has expressed concern that traffickers increasingly pose as legitimate ECOWAS traders, making detection difficult under current trade protocols (Adebayo, 2021).

Historically, criminal groups such as the **Hamani Tidjani gang**, operating across Nigeria, Togo, Benin, and Burkina Faso, leveraged the free movement policy to execute transnational carjacking and evade arrest. Similarly, **oil theft** in the Niger

Delta has evolved into an international enterprise involving actors from Venezuela, Lebanon, France, and Morocco, siphoning an estimated **\$3.5 billion annually** from Nigeria's economy (NEITI, 2020; Obi & Rustad, 2011). Despite the **ECOWAS Convention on Small Arms and Light Weapons (2006)**, enforcement has been weak. Nigeria has launched multiple military operations such as **Exercise Swift Response**, **Operation Sharan Daji**, and multilateral missions like **Operation Lake Sanity** in the Lake Chad Basin. However, these initiatives often fall short due to poor coordination, insufficient funding, lack of surveillance technology, and corruption within security agencies.

Collaboratively, the responses gathered during the key informant interview exercise reinforced and aligned with the earlier position.

Joint Response from Nigeria Customs and Immigration Officers (Northwest Border Commands Katsina, Sokoto, and Adamawa) maintained thus:

“The ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement, though intended for regional integration, has inadvertently enabled unchecked arms trafficking into Nigeria. Smugglers frequently pose as legitimate traders, herders, or migrants to conceal small arms in consignments of textiles, electronics, or food items. At entry points like the Jibia border in Katsina and Illela in Sokoto, weapons are moved through unofficial or poorly monitored routes. Customs officers are often constrained by outdated inspection tools, while immigration officers lack access to centralized biometric databases to screen travelers. The combined effect is the free inflow of weapons that fuel insurgency, armed robbery, and rural violence.”

In addition, the “Field operations in the Northeast regularly revealed foreign-manufactured weapons recovered from insurgent camps. These arms often trace back to routes from Chad, Libya, and Niger, smuggled into Nigeria with livestock or civilian cargo. Terrorist cells exploit the ECOWAS Protocol to cross borders undetected, regroup in neighboring states, and return armed for further attacks.

Intelligence reports also confirm that organized trafficking networks use informal trade corridors to move arms across borders with ease. Unfortunately, internal tracking systems for arms are either non-functional or plagued by corruption, making post-seizure investigations ineffective.

The sudden rise in armed banditry in Zamfara and neighboring states is linked directly to the influx of small arms from black markets in Niger. Bandits, once equipped with machetes and dane guns, now operate with AK-47s and other assault rifles. These weapons are smuggled under the cover of ECOWAS provisions, often during night movements, and without sufficient scrutiny. Arrested suspects frequently have no verifiable identity due to the lack of cross-border intelligence-sharing. Until ECOWAS integrates a regional arms control system, Nigeria will continue to face waves of violence from these lightly equipped but deadly groups.”

The absence of modern surveillance technologies such as drones, facial recognition systems, and real-time data sharing has made border policing ineffective. Corruption and political interference allow traffickers to bypass checkpoints with impunity. Meanwhile, the proliferation of arms has escalated not only violent crimes but also gender-based violence in rural areas. Women and girls in border communities are increasingly victimized by gangs who use these weapons to enforce control, demand ransom, and intimidate locals. The ECOWAS policy, without complementary human rights protections and law enforcement reforms, has exposed Nigeria’s most vulnerable populations to unchecked abuse.”

ECOWAS protocol on Establishment and Sustain Petroleum and other Product Smuggling in Nigeria. An Overview.

The ECOWAS Protocol on the Right of Establishment, outlined in Article 27 of the Revised ECOWAS Treaty (1993), permits citizens of member states to reside and engage in economic activities in other member states, subject to legal compliance and mutual reciprocity. While this provision aims to foster regional integration, it has inadvertently facilitated cross-border criminal activities, particularly petroleum smuggling in Nigeria. The country’s government-regulated fuel prices and heavy

subsidies have made it an attractive target for smugglers who exploit regional liberalization frameworks and institutional weaknesses.

One of the key drivers of fuel smuggling is the substantial price difference between subsidized petrol in Nigeria and the higher costs in neighboring countries such as Benin, Niger, and Cameroon. This disparity has created an underground economy where smuggling petroleum products becomes highly profitable. According to the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC, 2020), Nigeria's actual domestic fuel consumption is significantly overestimated, indicating large-scale diversion for illegal export. In 2019, the Nigerian Customs Service estimated that up to 10 million litres of petrol were smuggled out of Nigeria daily (Punch, 2019). These operations are often concealed under the guise of legitimate trade enabled by ECOWAS's free movement and trade protocols.

Law enforcement operations have repeatedly exposed the magnitude of the crisis. In 2021, Operation Swift Response, a multi-agency initiative, intercepted over 600 fuel tankers attempting to cross illegally into neighboring countries through porous borders in Ogun, Kebbi, and Katsina States (Daily Trust, 2021). Similarly, in 2023, the Nigerian Navy arrested several vessels near Lagos and Warri, carrying over 2 million litres of diverted petrol (Vanguard, 2023). In 2024, a smuggling ring in Adamawa State was dismantled after it was discovered that local marketers were collaborating with transporters to reroute petroleum products meant for domestic markets into Cameroon and Chad. A landmark case **The Republic v. Aboubacar Seydou** (ECOWAS Court of Justice, 2016) highlighted the legal tension between regional rights and national regulatory interests. In this case, an ECOWAS citizen arrested for engaging in cross-border fuel trading argued that his rights under the Protocol on Establishment were violated. While the court upheld the right to establish businesses, it emphasized that such activities must adhere to the domestic laws of host countries, especially in sensitive sectors like petroleum. This ruling underscores the legal complexities involved when regional integration intersects with illicit economic behavior.

Smuggling routes through border towns such as Idiroko (Ogun State), Illela (Sokoto State), and Jibia (Katsina State) have become notorious for illegal fuel trade. These

corridors serve as points where tankers are diverted and jerrycans are loaded for smuggling across poorly monitored crossings. The Nigerian Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (NEITI, 2021) reported that over ₦100 billion is lost annually due to petroleum smuggling, excluding broader economic costs from environmental degradation, corruption, and market distortions. The Nigerian government has made several efforts to curb this menace. The 2019 land border closure, under Operation Swift Response, aimed to disrupt fuel smuggling networks. The immediate impact was a significant drop in daily reported fuel consumption from 60 million litres to 52 million litres (NNPC, 2019), exposing the extent of smuggling. However, this unilateral action was criticized by ECOWAS institutions and neighboring countries for contradicting regional trade agreements (ECOWAS Commission, 2020).

Beyond petroleum, the liberal trade framework has also encouraged smuggling of other commodities such as textiles, rice, pharmaceuticals, and second-hand goods. These operations thrive in part due to inadequate customs inspections and bribery, further undermining Nigeria's economic stability. Okonkwo (2022) notes that border towns like Seme (Lagos State) and Illela (Sokoto State) are now major smuggling hubs where illegal goods move freely under the pretense of ECOWAS trade facilitation. According to the Nigeria Customs Service (NCS), the country loses over ₦200 billion annually in customs duties and taxes due to smuggling (Adebayo, 2021). These losses weaken public revenue needed for national infrastructure, education, and healthcare. Meanwhile, untaxed and substandard goods entering the market undercut local manufacturers, leading to factory closures, job losses, and the collapse of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Illicit financial flows (IFFs), including trade-based money laundering, also thrive under weak cross-border regulatory regimes. Criminal networks involved in fuel smuggling, arms trade, and drug trafficking use informal financial systems to conceal proceeds, exacerbating capital flight and economic instability. Olawale (2021) warns that unless coordinated efforts are made to trace and block these financial channels, Nigeria's development efforts will continue to suffer.

Despite these interventions, enforcement remains hampered by systemic corruption among border officials, limited technological infrastructure, and inconsistent regulatory enforcement. Smugglers have adapted by shifting to smaller vehicles and informal routes, making detection more difficult. Many of them exploit legal ambiguities in the ECOWAS Right of Establishment Protocol by registering shell companies to mask illegal activities. While the ECOWAS Protocol on Establishment was conceived to advance regional economic cooperation and development, its implementation without robust national safeguards has opened avenues for widespread cross-border criminality. Scholars like Akinterinwa (2018) and Adeoye (2021) advocate for a recalibrated integration framework one that harmonizes economic openness with strict regulatory oversight.

Collaboratively, the responses gathered during the key informant interview exercise reinforced and aligned with the earlier position.

Members of the Nigeria Security operatives in Illela Border Command Sokoto State maintained thus:

"The ECOWAS Protocol on Establishment allows individuals to set up businesses in member states, but smugglers have hijacked this framework. They register fake companies and use them as a cover for petroleum smuggling. We've intercepted several tankers labeled as 'local distribution' that were heading towards Benin Republic through bush paths. Our biggest challenge is that, once they show legal business papers, it becomes harder to enforce seizures without facing legal threats or diplomatic complaints."

Accordingly, most petroleum smugglers pose as cross-border traders operating under the ECOWAS establishment clause. With a registered business and an ECOWAS travel document, they blend in easily with genuine traders. The lack of a regional database or coordinated identity system means we can't verify the legitimacy of many of these so-called businesses. As a result, large volumes of petrol are smuggled daily to Niger Republic using legal businesses as fronts." He further added that "In

my intelligence tracking, we've identified petroleum smuggling rings using ECOWAS Protocol protections to shield their activities. These actors rent shops, register companies, and claim to be distributors yet they are deeply involved in cross-border fuel diversion. What's worse, they exploit legal loopholes and bribe their way through checkpoints. Our hands are tied because any enforcement seen as targeting ECOWAS citizens can create diplomatic tensions."

A personal from Nigerian Army Officer – Border Security Task Force (Adamawa State): "added that he encountered smuggling groups that operate as legally registered fuel marketers under ECOWAS provisions. They divert subsidized petrol from approved depots and distribute it across the borders to Cameroon and beyond. Once questioned, they present ECOWAS business documents. The protocol is being misused, and without a joint regional enforcement body, these economic criminals continue to weaken Nigeria's revenue base and national energy security." He further added that "Our patrols along the border have intercepted several trucks and small tankers loaded with petrol headed for Benin Republic. These vehicles are often owned by 'registered businesses' under ECOWAS trade laws. They exploit weak monitoring systems and legal ambiguity to operate freely. The challenge for us is not just in stopping them, but proving intent when their documents are technically in order. We need a regional policy revision to align free establishment rights with stricter security protocols."

Theoretical Framework

This study employs the Regional Security Complex Theory (RSCT) as its primary theoretical framework to analyze the security implications of the ECOWAS protocol within West Africa. Developed by Barry Buzan and OleWæver in the late 1980s and early 1990s, RSCT offers a robust analytical tool for understanding how security issues are interconnected within a specific regional context (Buzan &Wæver, 2003). According to RSCT, a regional security complex is defined by the interdependence of security concerns among states within a given region. This interdependence means that security issues in one state can significantly affect the security environment of neighboring states, leading to a network of security relationships (Buzan, 1991).

The theory asserts that while regional integration efforts such as those promoted by ECOWAS can enhance economic cooperation and political stability, they also introduce new vulnerabilities that can transcend national borders. These vulnerabilities often emerge from the unintended consequences of open borders and increased regional mobility. In the context of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), RSCT provides a valuable perspective on the dual nature of regional integration. On one hand, ECOWAS's protocols promote economic collaboration and political stability by fostering a common market and facilitating the free movement of people and goods. On the other hand, these same protocols can inadvertently expose member states to transnational security threats, such as cross-border crime, terrorism, and insurgencies (Buzan & Wæver, 2003). For example, the free movement of individuals within West Africa has been associated with increased trafficking in drugs and arms, which exacerbates security challenges in the region.

In Nigeria, RSCT helps elucidate the complex interplay between the benefits of regional integration and the security challenges it brings. The country's experience with insurgent groups such as Boko Haram and the Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP) illustrates how regional dynamics influence national security. The movement of fighters and resources across borders has compounded Nigeria's struggle with insurgency, demonstrating the vulnerability introduced by regional integration policies (Okpara, 2021). Additionally, the proliferation of small arms and light weapons in the West African region, partly facilitated by the open borders, has significantly impacted Nigeria's security landscape (UNODC, 2016). Furthermore, RSCT emphasizes that regional security complexes are shaped by both historical and contemporary factors, including colonial legacies, ethnic tensions, and economic disparities. In Nigeria, historical grievances and ethnic conflicts, combined with the challenges of managing a large and diverse population, underscore the relevance of RSCT in understanding the country's security issues within the broader West African context (Agbu, 2004). Conclusively, the theory offers a comprehensive framework for analyzing the security implications of the ECOWAS protocol. It highlights how regional integration, while fostering economic cooperation and political stability, also creates interconnected vulnerabilities that can exacerbate security challenges. In the

Nigerian context, RSCT provides valuable insights into the complex dynamics between the benefits of regional integration and

Study Findings

The findings from the study reveal significant unintended consequences of the ECOWAS protocols as they relate to security and economic stability in Nigeria. Regarding **Research Question One**, which asked whether the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons accounts for human trafficking in Nigeria, the study found that while the protocol was established to promote regional mobility and integration, it has inadvertently facilitated human trafficking activities. Data from the National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) and the International Organization for Migration (IOM) indicate that traffickers exploit Nigeria's porous borders and informal transport systems to move victims especially women and minors using fraudulent ECOWAS travel documents. Key border towns such as Seme, Jibia, and Illela have become hotspots for these activities due to weak surveillance and limited border control mechanisms.

For **Research objective two**, which examine whether the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods enhances illicit arms use in Nigeria, findings showed that while the protocol aims to promote regional trade and economic cooperation, it has created opportunities for the illegal smuggling of small arms and light weapons (SALWs). These weapons are frequently transported alongside legitimate goods through unmonitored or unofficial routes. States such as Zamfara, Borno, and Katsina have emerged as flashpoints for armed violence, largely due to the influx of smuggled arms. Nigeria now accounts for a considerable portion of the illicit weapons circulating in West Africa, with smugglers exploiting gaps in border control and cargo inspection.

In relation to **Research objective three**, which analyzed whether the ECOWAS Protocol on Establishment sustains petroleum and other product smuggling in Nigeria, the findings indicate that the protocol, which allows ECOWAS citizens to establish businesses across member states, has been widely abused. Smugglers set up front companies and use legitimate business documentation to transport subsidized

petroleum products from Nigeria to neighboring countries where fuel prices are higher. Major smuggling corridors include Ogun, Sokoto, and Katsina States. Reports from the Nigerian National Petroleum Company (NNPC) and the Nigeria Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (NEITI) affirm that Nigeria's fuel consumption figures are overstated due to large-scale product diversion, enabled by poor monitoring and weak enforcement of the establishment protocol.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the research question one study reveal a paradox inherent in the implementation of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons. While the Protocol was established in 1979 to promote regional integration, economic cooperation, and social cohesion among West African states, it has inadvertently created opportunities for transnational crimes, particularly human trafficking, to flourish across Nigeria's borders. Evidence from data sources such as the National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) and the International Organization for Migration (IOM) underscores how traffickers have taken advantage of the Protocol's provisions and existing border management weaknesses. Specifically, the absence of stringent cross-border verification systems has allowed traffickers to exploit legal channels of mobility using forged or fraudulently obtained ECOWAS travel documents. This exploitation is particularly evident in border communities like Seme in Lagos State, Jibia in Katsina State, and Illela in Sokoto State zones that serve as major transit corridors for trafficking due to limited surveillance and informal crossing points.

These findings align with existing scholarships emphasizing the unintended consequences of liberalized border policies in West Africa. According to Ojo (2019), the free movement protocols, without adequate security mechanisms, create vulnerabilities exploited by traffickers who use legal travel documents as cover. Similarly, Adesina and Adeoye (2021) argue that porous borders combined with weak institutional coordination foster an environment conducive to transnational crimes, including human trafficking. Their study highlights that traffickers capitalize on weak border governance and corruption among officials to circumvent detection.

Focus group discussions with security personnel in this study also mirror observations by scholars such as Onuoha (2017), who identifies institutional capacity gaps such as the lack of biometric systems, understaffing, and poor inter-agency collaboration as critical challenges undermining border security efforts. These vulnerabilities create loopholes that traffickers exploit under the guise of legitimate cross-border movement. Furthermore, the persistent trafficking challenges, despite ECOWAS's anti-trafficking frameworks, echo the findings of Iheduru (2020), who contends that regional protocols often suffer from implementation deficits due to weak political will and inadequate funding in member states. The gap between the policy design and on-the-ground enforcement leads to a scenario where traffickers operate with relative impunity.

The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC, 2022) underscores the necessity of harmonized regional responses, including the establishment of interoperable biometric databases and enhanced intelligence sharing among border agencies. This study supports those recommendations, emphasizing that without such reforms, the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons risks continuing to facilitate human trafficking rather than curtail it. In judicial terms, the ECOWAS Court of Justice has repeatedly stressed the importance of balancing regional integration with security concerns (ECOWAS Court, 2018). The Court advocates for member states to adopt complementary security measures that do not undermine the free movement principles but safeguard citizens against exploitation. This study confirms the dual-edge nature of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Persons: while promoting regional cooperation and socio-economic integration, its weak implementation and lack of robust border management have inadvertently sustained human trafficking networks in Nigeria. It reinforces the scholarly consensus on the urgent need for integrated regional security strategies, technological upgrades, and stronger institutional collaboration to protect vulnerable populations and uphold the protocol's intended benefits.

For research question two, the findings of this study revealed a significant unintended consequence of the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of Goods, which was primarily designed to facilitate trade liberalization and economic

integration within West Africa. Despite its positive economic intentions, the protocol has been exploited by criminal networks to facilitate the trafficking and proliferation of small arms and light weapons (SALWs) into Nigeria. These illicit arms movements often occur alongside legitimate goods, particularly through unregulated or unofficial border crossings, concealed within cargo or transported via informal bush paths. Border states such as Zamfara, Borno, and Katsina have become epicenters of violence, fueled by the influx of smuggled weapons that exacerbate armed banditry, insurgency, and communal conflicts.

This conclusion resonates with established scholarship on the nexus between regional trade liberalization and security vulnerabilities. As noted by Onuoha (2018), porous borders and weak customs enforcement have created enabling environments for the trafficking of arms that undermine regional security. Similarly, Obi and Ibekwe (2020) emphasize that weak inter-agency coordination and corrupt practices at checkpoints facilitate the seamless smuggling of weapons under the guise of legitimate trade facilitated by ECOWAS provisions. These conditions mirror the findings from focus group discussions involving Nigeria Customs Service, the military, and the Department of State Services (DSS), all of whom reported systemic enforcement weaknesses that insurgents and criminal gangs exploit. Further scholarly analysis by Ebo (2017) underlines Nigeria's disproportionate burden as a recipient of illicit arms within West Africa, attributing this partly to the absence of a centralized arms registry and ineffective enforcement of regional arms control measures. Although ECOWAS adopted the Convention on Small Arms and Light Weapons in 2006, scholars like Igbuzor (2019) argue that inconsistent implementation and limited coordination among member states continue to hamper efforts to control arms trafficking effectively.

The findings are also consistent with United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) reports, which document how illicit SALW flows in West Africa are frequently concealed beneath the veneer of legitimate commercial trade (UNODC, 2021). Without enhanced intelligence sharing, integrated tracking systems, and robust surveillance technologies, the illicit arms trade will persist as a destabilizing factor in Nigeria and the wider region. While the ECOWAS Protocol on Free

Movement of Goods serves important economic objectives, its poor enforcement has inadvertently turned it into a conduit for arms smugglers.

For research objective three, the findings reveal that the ECOWAS Protocol on the Right of Establishment, intended to encourage regional entrepreneurship, investment, and economic integration, has been exploited by criminal networks to facilitate the large-scale smuggling of petroleum products and other subsidized goods out of Nigeria. Although the protocol legally allows ECOWAS citizens to establish businesses across member states, the absence of effective oversight and verification mechanisms has enabled smugglers to register front companies and utilize legitimate trade documents to mask illicit cross-border product diversion. Reports from the Nigerian National Petroleum Company (NNPC) and the Nigeria Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (NEITI) highlight significant discrepancies between Nigeria's reported fuel consumption and actual domestic usage, largely attributable to smuggling activities. Key smuggling corridors identified include Ogun, Sokoto, and Katsina States border areas characterized by overstretched law enforcement and weak monitoring systems. These corridors serve as conduits for transporting subsidized fuel to neighboring countries where prices are substantially higher, creating strong economic incentives for illicit trade.

Participants in the focus group discussions (FGDs), which comprised customs officials, immigration officers, and security personnel, confirmed that many enterprises operating under the ECOWAS establishment right are in fact fronts for smuggling operations. A recurrent issue raised was the difficulty in distinguishing genuine businesses from fraudulent ones, particularly due to the lack of a centralized regional business verification database. Once smugglers secure valid registration and trade documents, enforcement agencies face legal and operational challenges in restricting their activities or seizing goods. These challenges are exacerbated by outdated surveillance technology, poor inter-agency cooperation, and widespread corruption at border checkpoints. Despite government efforts such as Operation Swift Response (launched in 2019) and partial border closures aimed at curbing smuggling, the study shows limited success in stemming the illicit trade. The persistence of smuggling networks is sustained by regulatory gaps at both national

and regional levels, weak enforcement of ECOWAS trade protocols, and the inability to conduct real-time monitoring of cross-border commercial activities.

These findings are supported by scholarly analyses. For example, Adeyemi and Oladele (2020) emphasize how the misuse of regional trade agreements and the establishment protocol facilitate smuggling, undermining national economic security. Similarly, Chukwu (2018) highlights the regulatory and enforcement challenges in controlling petroleum product smuggling within the West African sub-region, pointing to inadequate institutional frameworks and coordination failures. Furthermore, judicial decisions from the ECOWAS Court of Justice have recognized the delicate balance between promoting regional trade liberalization and safeguarding member states' economic interests, underscoring the need for stronger regulatory measures (ECOWAS Court, 2017). NEITI reports consistently reinforce concerns over the economic damage caused by unchecked product diversion and smuggling, which erode government revenues and destabilize local markets.

Conclusion

The ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement serves as a fundamental framework for promoting regional integration and economic cooperation among member states. However, its implementation in Nigeria has revealed critical security challenges, particularly concerning border management and transnational crime. This study concludes that while Nigeria has taken steps to mitigate these security threats, existing policies and enforcement mechanisms remain inadequate. The persistence of porous borders, weak institutional coordination, and limited surveillance capacity underscores the need for more robust security measures. Despite Nigeria's efforts, the increasing incidence of irregular migration, human trafficking, arms smuggling, and terrorism highlights the complexity of enforcing the protocol without compromising national security. The study concluded that while regional mobility has fostered economic benefits, it has also created vulnerabilities that require more strategic policy responses.

Recommendations

i. Establish a Regional Biometric Database

To effectively combat human trafficking facilitated by fraudulent ECOWAS travel documents, ECOWAS member states should collaborate to develop and implement a secure, interoperable biometric identity verification system at all border crossings. This will enhance the ability of border officials to accurately verify travelers' identities, close loopholes exploited by traffickers, and strengthen overall border security.

ii. Improve Cross-Border Intelligence Sharing

Given that illicit arms trafficking thrives on weak inter-agency cooperation and porous borders, ECOWAS and Nigerian security agencies should prioritize establishing robust intelligence-sharing frameworks. Enhanced real-time information exchange between customs, military, and law enforcement across borders will help identify and dismantle trafficking networks more effectively.

iii. Develop a Shared Regional Business Registry

To prevent the misuse of the ECOWAS right of establishment by smugglers using front companies, ECOWAS should establish a centralized regional business registry. This database would allow verification of business legitimacy across member states, making it easier for authorities to detect and disrupt smuggling operations disguised as legal trade.

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